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HYDROGEN (H₂) REDUCTION OF BAUXITE RESIDUE (“RED MUD”): FROM LABORATORY TO PILOT-SCALE

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Introduction

Bauxite residue (BR), also known as red mud, is a highly alkaline waste material generated during alumina production via the Bayer process, with global generation exceeding 170 million tonnes annually and stockpiles surpassing 5 billion tonnes^{1,2,3}. The chemical composition, rich in iron, aluminium, sodium, calcium, and titanium oxides, along with critical rare earth elements like scandium^{3,4,5}, presents both challenges and opportunities. BR poses significant environmental risks due to its fine particle size, high alkalinity, and limited reuse rates of less than 3%^{2,3}. Conventional disposal in landfills or ponds risks contamination and structural failures, while efforts to repurpose BR remain limited². Recent advancements have highlighted hydrogen reduction as a promising method for metal recovery, offering environmental benefits and efficient extraction of various metals^{3,5,6,7,9}. Our recent laboratory-scale study optimised a low-temperature H₂ reduction roasting process at 600°C, followed by combined water leaching and magnetic separation, achieving significant recoveries of Fe (74.4%), Al (84.6%), and Na (91.6%)^{8,9}. Building on these lab-scale findings, a pilot-scale tilted rotary induction furnace for H₂ reduction roasting was developed and presented herein, successfully producing magnetite and sodium aluminate from BR pellets. Optimal recovery of iron as magnetite, and aluminium and sodium as sodium aluminate, can be achieved by leaving a non-magnetic fraction rich in Si, Ti, Ca, and Sc using a subsequent process involving wet milling followed by magnetic separation at 0.15 T. These findings could highlight a scalable and sustainable route for transforming BR into a valuable resource while addressing its environmental footprint.

Methodology

BR from Metlen Energy & Metals, Greece, was oven-dried at 110°C to remove moisture and then homogenised. Pelletisation was optimised using a 12 L ploughshare mixer, blending 20 wt% NaOH with 100 wt% BR to produce pellets sized between 10–20 mm (Figure 1c). These pellets were dried before undergoing high-temperature H₂ reduction roasting in a custom-built 200 kW hydraulic induction furnace (Figure 1a). The furnace featured a rotating SiC crucible lined with refractory concrete, into which a gas-tight stainless steel metal crucible with internal baffles was inserted as a sleeve. The SiC

crucible was retained, although it is redundant, as the metal crucible directly couples with the induction field. This setup allowed for precise control of gas atmospheres, including 100% N₂, 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂, and 100% H₂, at pressures up to 0.5 bar.

Figure 1: Pilot scale trails: a) 200 kW hydraulic rotating induction furnace (70 L) at 0° position, b) rotating induction furnace during H₂ reduction operation at 90° position c) pellets produced through plough shear mixer, d) roasted pellets after H₂ reduction

The furnace was tilted and rotated intermittently to ensure uniform heating (Figure 1b). During reduction, a gas mixture of 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂ was introduced at 600°C, stabilised with 15–20 kW of power. Process parameters such as H₂ flow rate (1-20 LPM), furnace angle (45°, 90°), pressure, and pellet input (up to 35 kg per batch) were optimised through pilot-scale trials. Following reduction, the roasted pellets (Figure 1d) underwent wet milling in a 5 litre attritor mill with a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:1.15, with filtration (12 µm, 0.45 µm) separating Al- and Na-depleted solids from sodium aluminate-enriched leachate. Wet-magnetic separation (0.15 T) was applied to the solid fraction, producing magnetic and non-magnetic products, both of which were dried. The final products during H₂ reduction roasting and after separation were extensively analysed using techniques including XRD, SEM-EDS, ICP-OES, EPMA, WD-XRF, TGA, and laser particle size analysis. The recovery efficiencies for Fe (Fe grade), Al, and Na were calculated using specific Equations (1), (2), and (3), (4) respectively.

$$Fe \text{ Recovery } (\%) = \frac{C * c}{(F * f)} * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Fe \text{ Grade } (\%) = \frac{(Total \ mass \ of \ Fe)}{(Total \ sample \ mass)} * 100 \quad Fe \text{ Recovery } (\%) = \frac{C*c}{(F*f)} * 100 \quad (2)$$

$$Al \text{ Recovery}(\%) = \frac{(cL * VL)}{((cL * VL) + (CSR * mSR))} * 100 \quad (3)$$

$$Na\ Recovery(\%) = \frac{(cL * VL)}{((cL * VL) + (TNa * mSR))} * 100 \quad (4)$$

The abbreviations in the equations are the following: C: weight of the concentrate (grade); c: assay of concentrate (%); F: weight of Feed (grade); f: assay of grade (%); cL: concentration of elements in leachate solution (mg/mL); VL: amount of leachate solution (mL); CSR: concentration of elements in the solid residue (mg/g); mSR: mass of solid fraction(g); TNa = total Na in the system (mg) including both Na present in the Raw BR and the sodium added via NaOH to raw BR.

Results and Discussion

The detailed characterisation of as-received BR is reported elsewhere^{8,9}. During H₂ reduction the target is to maximise the magnetite and sodium aluminate formation in the roasted pellets. The scaled-up trials at optimised conditions (600°C, 4 h, 90° rotation angle, and 20 LPM of 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂) resulted in complete hematite-to-magnetite conversion (100%) and sodium aluminate presence in the pellets. To enhance productivity, the estimated time required for processing each metallic crucible with loaded pellets, from insertion into the induction furnace to extraction, is approximately 4.5 to 5 h. This includes 10 min for loading the raw materials, 30-40 min for heating to 600°C, and 4 h for the reduction process. With interchangeable metallic crucibles and continuous operation, it is feasible to process multiple batches simultaneously, enabling a throughput of 180-200 kg/day. A 30 min milling duration of pilot scale roasted samples achieved high recovery rates (Table 1) of Fe (77.8%), Al (54.7%), and Na (66.7%). The reduced liquid volume after the filtration method led to more concentrated Al and Na solutions (127.6 g/L Al, 120.0 g/L Na) compared to the lab scale process (16.5 g/L Al, 14.0 g/L Na), relevant for Bayer process applications. Magnetic separation resulted in a magnetite-rich fraction with a grade of up to 54%, while non-magnetic tailings were enriched with CaO, SiO₂, and TiO₂. Processing 1 ton of BR yielded 491.4 kg of magnetite, 372.2 kg of tailings, and 196.3 kg of NaAlO₂.

Table 1: Comparison of lab scale route and pilot scale produced pellets routes with two different approaches

Method	Lab scale	Pilot scale
	H ₂ roasted pellets – wet milling – combined water leaching magnetic separation – filtration ⁹	H ₂ roasted pellets – wet milling – Filtration-wet magnetic separation [current method]
Fe recovery (%)	74.4	77.8
Fe grade (%)	63.6	53.4
Al recovery (%)	84.6	54.7
Na recovery (%)	91.6	66.7

Conclusions

Pilot-scale hydrogen reduction roasting of bauxite residue (BR) was successfully carried out at 600°C, using 20 wt% NaOH and 5% H₂ (20 LPM), achieving full hematite and goethite conversion to magnetite and concurrent production of sodium aluminate. This process efficiently recovered Fe (magnetite), Al, and Na, with non-magnetic tailings enriched in Si, Ca, and Ti. A total of 150 kg of roasted pellets were produced in batch trials, resulting in 77.8% Fe recovery at a 55% Fe grade, and 54.7% Al and 67% Na recoveries. The process, utilising only 33 kW (16.5%) of total 200 kW rotary induction furnace power, demonstrated stable performance, offering a scalable, low-emission, environmentally sustainable method for producing magnetite and sodium aluminate-rich pellets from BR, with potential for industrial application and integration into metallurgical and construction sectors.

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